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Rahim Thawer - Queer Mental Health Media Archive

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Abstract

Reflects on the necessary integration between clinical practice and political positioning when working with marginalized populations. Argues that therapeutic neutrality can perpetuate oppressions when structural power dynamics aren't recognized. Proposes a model of informed clinical advocacy that validates discrimination experiences while strengthening individual agency, balancing political validation with concrete psychological tools.

Keywords

social justice, clinical practice, intersectionality

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